

Preparation of 3-phenyl-5-(1'-acetyl-1'-carboethoxy methyl) rhodanine (III): 3-Phenyl-5-mono-bromorhodanine (0.01 mole) and acetoacetic ester (0.01 mole) were taken in ethanol and refluxed on a water bath for 8 hrs. Excess ethanol was evaporated, cooled and cold water was added. The brown coloured compound thus obtained was filtered, crystallised from glacial acetic acid, m.p. 121°. Gives colouration with FeCl_3 solution, soluble in 10% aq. alkali and gives positive test for ester group ($\text{C}_{15}\text{NS}_2\text{O}_4\text{H}_{15}$ requires, C, 53.40; H, 4.41; N, 4.12; Found C, 53.02; H, 4.23; N, 3.99%).

Preparation of 3-phenyl-5-(1'-phenyl-3'-methyl-5-one) rhodanine: Method I: 3-Phenyl-5-(1'-acetyl-1'-carboethoxy methyl) rhodanine (0.01 mole) was dissolved in minimum quantity of acetic acid. Phenyl hydrazine (0.01 mole) was added to it and the mixture heated for 1 hr on a water bath, cooled and the resulting mixture filtered and crystallised from acetone. Yield 50%, soluble in 10% aq. alkali and gave colouration with FeCl_3 .

Method II: 5-Mono-bromo-3-phenyl-rhodanine (0.01 mole) and 1-phenyl-3-methyl-2-pyrazolin-5-one (0.01 mole) were taken in 25 ml of ethanol followed by fused sodium acetate and refluxed for 4 hrs on a water bath. Excess ethanol was evaporated and the resulting mixture cooled and ice-cold water was added to it. The gummy product was dissolved in 10% aqueous alkali, filtered and the filtrate was acidified with cold dil. HCl. The white compound thus obtained was filtered and crystallised from acetone, soluble in 10% aq. alkali and gave colouration with FeCl_3 solution.

Method III: 1-Phenyl-3-methyl-2-pyrazolin-4-mono-bromo-5-one (0.01 mole) and 3-phenyl-rhodanine (0.01 mole) were taken in 25 ml of ethanol followed by fused sodium acetate and refluxed for 4 hrs on a water bath. The excess ethanol was evaporated and cooled. Ice-cold water was added to it. The gummy mass obtained was dissolved in 10% aq. alkali and acidified with cold dil. HCl. The white compound thus obtained was crystallised from acetone, soluble in 10% aq. alkali and gave colouration with FeCl_3 solution.

The m.p. of the compounds obtained by the three methods was found to be the same and the ir data superimposable with each other. The ir data show the enolic band at 3012 cm^{-1} and the band at 1597 cm^{-1} (ring $> \text{C}=\text{O}$).

Preparation of the oxidation product of 3-phenyl-5-(1'-phenyl-3'-methyl-2'-pyrazolin-5'-one) rhodanine: 3-Phenyl-5-(1'-phenyl-3'-methyl-2'-pyrazolin-5'-one) (2 g) was dissolved in 10% sodium hydroxide solution (20 ml). A saturated solution of iodine in potassium iodide (25 ml) was added with constant stirring for 1 hr. The light blue compound thus obtained was filtered, washed with 10% solution of sodium thiosulphate, finally with water and purified from acetone. Yield 75%. IR data show the presence of ($> \text{C}=\text{O}$) band at 1620 cm^{-1} , enolic band absent.

Following the above procedure we have synthesised ten bis compounds and their ten oxidation product whose physical and fungicidal data are given in the Table 1 and Table 2 respectively.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to the Director, Central Rice Research Institute, Cuttack for providing necessary facilities for carrying out the fungicidal test.

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Synthesis and Fungitoxicity of Substituted Pyrazolyl Oxazole

SUNDAR RAO* and A. S. MITTRA

Department of Chemistry, Ravenshaw College, Cuttack-753 003

Manuscript received 16 July 1980, revised 27 January 1981, accepted 15 July 1981

Oxazole have been associated with hypertensive¹, analgesic, antiinflammatory^{2,3}, antibacterial, antiviral⁴, antitubercular⁵, anticonvulsant⁶ and antifungal⁷ activities. In our earlier investigation on heterocyclic fungicides⁸⁻¹¹ it was noted that 5-pyrazolone possess significant fungicidal activity against the rice blast pathogen *Pyricularia oryzae* and the brown leaf spot pathogen *Helminthosporium oryzae*. Significant fungicidal activity exhibited by pyrazolyl-thiazole¹²⁻¹³ against the above pathogens encouraged us to synthesise a new heterocyclic compound containing both pyrazolone and oxazole moieties with a view to study and compare its fungitoxicity with the corresponding sulphur analogue. The structure of ten compounds thus prepared have been established from satisfactory analytical values, solubility in aq. NaOH and positive test with ethanolic FeCl_3 . IR spectra (cm^{-1}) of Cpd No 2 showed characteristic absorption bands around 3000 (NH coupled with aromatic C-H vibration), 1650 ($\text{C}=\text{O}$), 1610 (phenyl ring) and at 1535 ($\text{C}=\text{C}$). Absence of enolic hydroxyl absorption indicates that in solid state it remains as carbonyl compound but in solution it exists as a mixture of tautomer. The compounds were screened for their antifungal activity against *Pyricularia oryzae* and *Helminthosporium oryzae* by standard method¹⁴ using spore germination tests

* Present address: Chemistry Department, Govt. College, Angul-759 143 (Orissa).

